
Modelling adsorption and transport behaviour of gases in moist coal matrix

Min Chen*, Shakil Masum, Hywel Thomas

Geoenvironmental Research Centre, Cardiff School of Engineering, Cardiff University, Queen's Buildings, The Parade, Newport Road, CF24 3AA, Cardiff, UK

Corresponding author: Min Chen (Email: Chenm24@cardiff.ac.uk)

Abstract

Water is ubiquitous in coalbeds, and its influence on coalbed carbon sequestration and/or methane recovery cannot be neglected. In order to investigate the roles of moisture content in gas transport and adsorption behaviour, this paper presents a mass transport model for real gas transport in moist coal matrix based on multiple transport mechanisms. A modified kinetics in conjunction with Langmuir isotherm is proposed to incorporate the effects of moisture and it is used to describe the mass change between bulk phase and adsorbed phase gases. The reliability of the model has been demonstrated through validation exercises. The results indicate that moisture in coal matrices alters both volume constant and pressure constant in conjunction with Langmuir isotherm. The presence of moisture can significantly reduce the gas adsorption capacity, and hinder the loss of bulk gas diffusivity. The moisture effects on gas diffusion kinetics are associated with applied pressure, pore size, as well as the moisture contents. Larger pressures and pores can shorten the time for reaching equilibrium state. The moisture effects on the time required to reach equilibrium is more significant when pore sizes are smaller. The required time for adsorbed gas concentration reaching equilibrium is found to be shorter than that for the gas pressure due to the role of surface diffusion.

Keywords: modelling, gas diffusion; adsorption; coal matrix, inherent moisture

1 Introduction

Research in coalbeds have attracted numerous attentions in recent decades, due to their positive contributions on global energy supply as well as for being target formations for geological carbon dioxide (CO₂) sequestration.^{1, 2} Coalbed is a naturally fractured porous medium, and usually characterized as a dual porosity system with well-defined and nearly uniformly distributed network of fractures and porous matrix blocks containing a multiscale pore structures.^{3, 4} The pore structure of a coal matrix is highly heterogeneous, ranging from a few nanometres to over micrometres. The

International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) divided coal pores into three categories: micropores (≤ 2 nm), mesopores (2-50 nm) and macropores (> 50 nm).⁵ Some of studies observed that micropores, especially the ultra micropores (< 1 nm) accounts for a considerable portion of coal pore system.⁶⁻⁸ Most of internal surface area is provided by micropores with strong affinity to gasses, such as methane (CH_4) and CO_2 .^{9, 10} However, the presence of water/moisture in coal could lead to complex gas adsorption behaviour. Water is ubiquitous in coalbeds, therefore, detailed understanding of gas transport phenomena in moist coals are of significant importance both for coal seam gas production and for CO_2 storage.

Gas transport in coal matrices is dominated by the two important processes, e.g., gas adsorption/desorption, and diffusion. The influence of moisture on these processes have been estimated in laboratory experiments.^{8, 11-24} Crosdale et al.¹² used a volumetric technique to measure the methane adsorption capacity of subbituminous coal samples of various moisture contents. They observed that the adsorption capacity of methane decreased from 34 to 13.5 cm^3/g , and 29.88 to 10.2 cm^3/g when the relative humidity increased from 15 % to 96% for coal samples from Kupakupa seam and Renown seam of New Zealand, respectively. Similar impact of moisture on gas adsorption capacity is also observed in the other studies. The loss of adsorption capacity occurs because the coal moisture occupies a proportion of the available sorption sites for gas molecules in the matrix, and hence blocks the access of gas molecules to the pore surfaces.^{8, 25} Joubert et al.²⁶ and Levy et al.²⁷ reported that the adsorption capacity decreases linearly with increasing coal moisture contents. But in recent studies,^{8, 12, 19, 20} a nonlinear relationship has been observed. Chen et al.²⁸ proposed an exponential relationship to quantify the nonlinear effect of moisture on the gas adsorption capacity. The effect of moisture on gas adsorption capacity also depends on the coal rank. The hydrophilic and hydrophobic compositions in coals vary with coal rank.²⁰ In moist coals, gas sorption capacity increases with coal rank.^{11, 15, 29} In contrary, the adsorption capacity in dry coals show a typical 'U-shape' dependence on rank.^{11, 29} Lower rank coals are more affected by the presence of coal moisture than the higher rank coals.¹⁷ In addition, the effects of moisture on adsorption capacity of different gases are also distinct. It is reported that the reduction in adsorption capacity of CH_4 due to presence of moisture is greater than that of the CO_2 .^{17, 19} The moisture-induced reduction of gas adsorption capacity ceases at a critical moisture content, beyond which further moisture increase does not affect

the adsorption capacity,¹⁷ similar observations were also reported by Joubert et al.²⁶ and Pajdak⁸. This was interpreted as all hydrophilic sites have been occupied by moisture, the excess moisture was located on the external surface of the coal and did not affect the sorption further by blocking the pores.¹¹ This critical moisture content depends on the rank of the coal and sorption pressure. The influence of moisture on the sorption capacity is highest at low pressures, increasing the sorption equilibrium pressure can decrease the moisture induced reduction of sorption capacity of coal.^{8, 15}

The previous studies largely focused on the impact of coal moisture on gas adsorption capacity. Only a few studies investigated gas diffusion kinetics in moist coals. In these studies, the presence of moisture is found to lessen gas diffusivity or its sorption rates.^{19, 30-32} Thimons and Kissell³³ believed that the accumulation of water by multilayer adsorption and capillary condensation results in a reduction of the pore radii and/ or block the pores by forming water cluster, this eventually leads to a reduction of gas diffusion rates. According to Pan et al.¹⁹, it takes a few hours for sorption to reach 80% of the total amount on the coal with 8.5% moisture content, while it only takes a few minutes on the dry coal. An increase in gas diffusivity with an increase in moisture content was found by Švábová et al.¹³. Similar result was also reported by Wang et al.³⁴. This behaviour is explained by the fact that higher energy polar sites are preferentially occupied by water, which in turn reduces the sorption capacity of coal and accelerates gas diffusion in the pore space.¹³ In addition, the experimental studies by Wang et al.¹⁴ indicate that the moisture effects on diffusion kinetics are also associated with coal rank. For the anthracite coals, diffusivity decreases with increasing moisture content, while it varies with the moisture content according to a U-shape function for the bituminous coal. Moreover, the impact of moisture content on the diffusion rate is stronger for CH₄ than CO₂ in bituminous coals. It is evident that gas transport and adsorption processes in moist coals are significantly complex, therefore, further investigations are required for comprehensive understanding of these processes.

Generally, moisture exists in coal as different states, the classification method for coal moisture is not consistent in literature. For example, Roux and Campbell presented one of classification methods for forms of water in coals:³⁵ surface or free moisture (water held on the surface of coal particles or macerals), inherent or capillary moisture (moisture allocated within the pores of each individual particle), chemically bound moisture (water which comprises part of the

chemical structure of the ash fraction of the coal, as crystal water for example). Pan et al. described the moisture in the fractures as free moisture and moisture in the coal matrix as inherent moisture.¹⁹ More detailed classification of water in coal can be found in work by Yu et al.³⁶ Moisture in coal matrix pores can form multilayers of adsorbed molecules.³⁷ on the other hand, gas molecules adsorbed at the interface between the pore solid and the free gas phase, which were not occupied by moisture, forms the adsorbed phase, while the free molecules in the pore void forms the bulk gas phase. The coexistence of these phases makes gas transport in moist coal matrices more complex.

The purpose of this study is to develop a predictive model for investigating gas transport processes in moist coal matrices. Previously published model of Chen et al.,³⁸ which predicts gas migration behaviour in dry coal matrices, is extended in this work. Gas diffusion and adsorption kinetics, which are mostly ignored in existing literatures, are included in the model. A nonlinear relationship is used here to describe the influence of coal moisture contents on its gas adsorption capacity. To account mass exchange between adsorbed and free gas phases, a modified kinetics based on Langmuir isotherm is proposed. The impacts of moisture on the gas diffusion behaviour are analyzed in this work. The model is applicable for studying gas migration behaviour in moist coals with inherent water contents. In the subsequent sections, firstly, the governing equations of both gas phases are presented. Secondly, the proposed model is validated against experimental results and, finally, the model is applied to investigate the effects of moisture on gas transport processes in moist coal matrices.

2 Model development

2.1 Model assumptions

It is assumed that the adsorbed and bulk gas phases coexist in coal matrices, and the principle of mass conservation is applicable to individual phases. Gas dissolution in inherent coal moisture is found to be significantly low.^{17,39} Therefore, gas dissolution in the matrix porewater is ignored in this work. Gas adsorption/desorption behavior can be adequately described by kinetics in conjunction with Langmuir model.

2.2 Governing equation of bulk gas transport

Bulk gas transport in the nanopores of a porous media includes viscous flow and Knudsen diffusion.^{38,40} The mechanisms contribute either individually or simultaneously under certain temperature-pressure conditions. In order to calculate their contributions in the bulk gas transport, Wu et al.⁴⁰ defined the total gas flux using a Knudsen number-based weighting factor as:

$$J_f = \omega_K J_{fK} + \omega_v J_{fv} \quad (1)$$

where J_f is the total gas flux in the free phase, J_{fK} is the Knudsen diffusion flux, and J_{fv} is the viscous flux. ω_v and ω_K are weighting factors for viscous flux and Knudsen flux respectively, which are defined as:

$$\omega_v = \frac{1}{1 + K_n} \quad (2)$$

$$\omega_K = \frac{1}{1 + 1/K_n} \quad (3)$$

Knudsen number (K_n) is defined as the ratio of a molecular mean free path to the average pore diameter:⁴¹

$$K_n = \frac{\lambda}{2r_e} \quad (4)$$

where λ is the mean free path of molecules, and r_e is the effective radius of a pore that accounts the diameter of adsorbed gas molecules and the thickness of the moisture layer in the pore (Fig.1b). For a real gas, λ can be expressed as:⁴²

$$\lambda = \frac{\mu}{u} \sqrt{\frac{\pi ZRT}{2M}} \quad (5)$$

where u is the gas pressure, μ is the gas viscosity, R is the universal gas constant, and M is the molar weight, T is absolute temperature, Z is the gas compressibility factor. In this work, the compressibility factor is calculated following the Equations of State proposed by Peng and Robinson.⁴³ The gas pressure is expressed as:

$$u = ZRTC \quad (6)$$

where C is the concentration of the free/bulk gas phase.

Knudsen diffusion is generally described using Fick's law as:

$$J_{fK} = -D_K \nabla C \quad (7)$$

where D_K is the Knudsen diffusion coefficient and it is calculated following Darabi et al.⁴⁴ as:

$$D_K = \frac{2r_e n_e}{3 \tau} \left(\frac{d_m}{2r_e} \right)^{d_f-2} \sqrt{\frac{8ZRT}{\pi M}} \quad (8)$$

where n_e is the effective porosity, τ is tortuosity of the medium, d_f is the fractal dimension of the pore surface accounting for the effect of pore-surface roughness on the Knudsen diffusion coefficient, d_f varies between 2 and 3, representing a smooth surface and a space-filling surface, respectively,⁴⁴ d_m is the molecular size.

Fig. 1 Schematic illustration of the effective radius of the pores: (a) distribution of adsorbed gas and water inside a pore and (b) equivalent volume of space occupied by adsorbed gas and water.

Adsorption of gas molecules and moisture onto the pore wall reduces the available spaces for bulk gas flow (Fig.1a). To obtain the effective radius of pores, an equivalent model is used: given that the adsorbed gas molecules create a single layer covering part of the pore wall surface, and the space occupied by gas adsorption is assumed to be equivalent to area of the green ring in Fig. 2(b), and the space occupied by water is equivalent to the area of blue ring (Fig.1b). Hence, the effective pore radius and the effective porosity (n_e) are written as:⁴⁵

$$r_e = r_h - r_w - r_a \quad (9)$$

$$n_e = n \left(\frac{r_e}{r_h} \right)^2 \quad (10)$$

where n is the porosity of coal matrices in absence of adsorbed gas and water, r_h is the hydraulic radius of the pore, r_w is the equivalent thickness of the water film, and r_a is the

equivalent thickness of the adsorbed gas layer. Following Xiong et al.⁴⁶, r_a can be expressed as:

$$r_a = d_m \theta \quad (11)$$

where θ is the gas coverage on the wall of matrix pores.

It is assumed that the gas adsorption behavior obeys the Langmuir adsorption isotherm and, therefore, the gas coverage can be described as:

$$\theta = \frac{C_s}{C_{Ld}} \quad (12)$$

where C_s is the adsorbed phase concentration, C_{Ld} is the maximum adsorbed phase concentration of dry coals.

From Fig. 2(b), the correlation between equivalent water film thickness and water saturation can be derived as:⁴⁷

$$S_w = \frac{(r_h - r_a)^2 - (r_h - r_a - r_w)^2}{r_h^2} \quad (13)$$

The gravimetric moisture content, m_w , defined as a ratio of total water mass to the total mass of the dry material, is commonly used to represent the amount of water in materials. It can be expressed as:

$$m_w = S_w \bar{\rho}_w V_{pv} \quad (14)$$

where $\bar{\rho}_w$ is average density of water film and V_{pv} is pore volume per unit mass of materials.

The viscous gas flux or slip flow can be expressed with Darcy's law as:^{40, 45}

$$J_{fv} = -\frac{n_e r_e^2}{\tau 8\mu} (1 + \alpha K_n) \left(1 + \frac{4K_n}{1 - bK_n}\right) C \nabla u \quad (15)$$

where b is the slip coefficient (here $b = -1$) to account for slippage effect, α is the rarefaction coefficient. The dimensionless rarefaction coefficient is explained empirically by Civan⁴⁸:

$$\alpha = 1.358 \left(1 + \frac{0.178}{K_n^{0.4348}}\right)^{-1} \quad (16)$$

The gas viscosity, μ , of real gases is obtained from the model of Lee et al.⁴⁹:

$$\mu = 10^{-4} K \exp[X\rho^Y] \quad (17)$$

$$K = \frac{(9.379 + 0.01607M)T^{1.5}}{209.2 + 19.26M + T} \quad (18)$$

$$X = 3.448 + 0.01009M + \frac{986.4}{T} \quad (19)$$

$$Y = 2.447 - 0.2224X \quad (20)$$

$$\rho = \frac{uM}{ZRT} \quad (21)$$

Substitution of equations (6) and (10) into equation (15) yields:

$$J_{fv} = -D_v \nabla C \quad (22)$$

$$D_v = \left(\frac{r_e}{r_h}\right)^4 \frac{k_\infty}{\mu} u(1 + \alpha K_n) \left(1 + \frac{4K_n}{1 - bK_n}\right) \left(1 + \frac{C}{Z} \frac{\partial Z}{\partial C}\right) \quad (23)$$

where $k_\infty = \frac{n r_h^2}{\tau 8}$ represents the intrinsic permeability of porous media.

Finally, the governing equation of bulk/ free gas flow is expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial(n_e C)}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot J_f - S \quad (22)$$

where S is the sink/source representing mass transfer from the bulk phase to the adsorbed phase. The sink/source term has been detailed later.

2.3 Governing equation of adsorbed gas flow

In this work, surface diffusion is assumed to be the dominant mode of transport for adsorbed gas molecules, and it is driven by the adsorbed gas concentration gradient.^{40, 46} The surface diffusion flux is written as:

$$J_s = -(1 - n)D_s \nabla C_s \quad (24)$$

where J_s is the surface diffusion flux, D_s is the surface diffusion coefficient.

Surface diffusivity is a function of temperature, surface gas concentration, the interaction between the adsorbate and the solid surface, as well as the structure of the solid surface.⁵⁰ Based on the transition state theory, Chen and Yang⁵¹ proposed the following kinetic method to capture the concentration dependency of the surface diffusivity:

$$D_s = D_s^0 \frac{1 - \theta + \frac{w}{2}\theta(1 - \theta) + (1 - w)\frac{w}{2}\theta^2 H(1 - w)}{\left(1 - \theta + \frac{w}{2}\theta\right)^2} \quad (25)$$

$$H(1 - w) = \begin{cases} 0 & w \geq 1 \\ 1 & 0 \leq w \leq 1 \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

where D_s^0 is the surface diffusivity at zero coverage, which is a function of temperature and gas activation energy. $H(1 - w)$ is the Heaviside function, w is a measure of the degree of blockage by another adsorbed molecule and it is defined as the ratio of the rate of blockage to the rate of forward migration:

$$w = \frac{w_b}{w_m} \quad (27)$$

where w_b is the rate constant for blockage of surface gas molecule, w_m is the rate constant for forward migration of surface gas molecule. When $w_m > w_b$, i.e. $w < 1$, surface diffusion occurs regardless the forward position. When $w_m < w_b$, i.e. $w > 1$, gas molecules are blocked and surface diffusion stops. Chen and Yang's Model for non-zero w can yield many patterns for the surface diffusivity variation with loading. For surface diffusion where there is no effective blockage, the transport surface diffusivity reduces to that of the classic HIO or Darken theory.⁵² Fig. 2 shows the relationship between surface diffusivity and coverage for different ratios of the rate of blockage to the rate of forward migration (i.e., Eq.25 and 26).

Fig. 2 Changes of surface diffusion coefficient with gas coverage.

The governing mass conservation equation of the adsorbed gas phase can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial[(1 - n)C_s]}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot J_s + S \quad (28)$$

where C_s is the adsorbed phase concentration.

2.4 Mass exchange between two phases

It is assumed that gas adsorption behavior can be characterized by the kinetics in conjunction with Langmuir model. It suggests that the process of gas penetration and evaporation from surface of micropores can be viewed as infinite mass interchange between adsorbed and free phase.⁵³ The gas adsorption rate and desorption rate are expressed as:

$$R_a = \gamma_a u(C_L - C_s) \quad (29)$$

$$R_d = \gamma_d C_s \quad (30)$$

where R_a and R_d are the rates of adsorption and desorption, γ_a and γ_d are the rate constant for adsorption and desorption, respectively, C_L is the adsorption capacity of a moist coal.

Therefore, the net rate of adsorption R_{net} , can be given as:

$$R_{net} = R_a - R_d = \gamma_d [B_L u(C_L - C_s) - C_s] \quad (31)$$

where $\gamma_a/\gamma_d = B_L$, is the reciprocal of pressure constant in conjunction with Langmuir model u_L , at which half of the C_L of the gas that can be adsorbed.

The impact of moisture on the gas adsorption can be described with an exponential decay equation,⁸ written as:

$$C_L = C_{L0} + C_{Lm} \exp(-\varphi m_w) \quad 0 < m_w < m_c \quad (32)$$

where C_{L0} represents the maximum amount of gases adsorbed on the sites that are exclusive to gas molecules, C_{Lm} represents the maximum amount of gases adsorbed on the sites that have potential to moisture adsorption when the moisture is present, m_c is the critical moisture content of the coal, beyond which the sorption capacity is not affected by further moisture increase, and φ is the adsorption capacity decay coefficient, its value is associated with coal compositions, which can be determined from matching the experimental data.

As discussed above, the mass exchange between free and adsorbed phases is associated with gas adsorption and desorption. Thereby, the second term in equations (22) and (28) can be given as:⁵⁴

$$S = (1 - n)\gamma_d [B_L u(C_L - C_s) - C_s] \quad (33)$$

2.5 Computational approach

In present study, the developed model is implemented into an in-house numerical modelling code, COMPASS, developed by Thomas and coworkers.^{38, 55} The partial differential equations are expressed in terms of the primary model variables C , C_s . The Galerkin Finite Element method is used spatially discretise the equations, while an implicit mid-interval backward difference scheme is used to achieve temporal discretization of the governing partial differential equations. The numerical solution calculated by COMPASS will be tested subsequently.

3 Model validation

3.1 Adsorption isotherms for dry and wet coal samples

Pajdak⁸ investigated the effects of moisture on CO₂ sorption behaviour in bituminous coals. The laboratory samples were collected from three different coal mines in the Upper Silesian Coal Basin of Poland: Sobieski coal mine (SOB-PL), Silesia coal mine (SIL-PL) and Brzeszcze coal mine (BRZ-PL). The samples were crushed and sieved into 0.2–0.25 mm grain size and then moisturized for the tests. Tests were carried out under isothermal (313 K) condition and pressures from 0.1 MPa to 0.8 MPa. The experimental sorption results are used in validation exercises.

When gas sorption reaches equilibrium, i.e. $S = 0$ in equation (33). Combining equation (32), equation (33) can be reduced to (Model A):

$$C_s = \frac{[C_{L0} + C_{Lm} \exp(-\lambda m_w)] B_L u}{1 + B_L u}, \quad 0 < m_w < m_c \quad (34)$$

To quantify the nonlinear effect of moisture on the gas adsorption capacity, Chen et al.²⁸ proposed an exponential model, given as (Model B):

$$C_s = \frac{C_{Lm} \exp(-\lambda m_w) B_L u}{1 + B_L u}, \quad 0 < m_w < m_c \quad (35)$$

Equation (34) and (35) are used to match analytically the results of Pajdak⁸. The parameters obtained by fitting the experimental data are listed in Table 1. The comparison between model predictions and experimental results about moisture- and pressure-dependent adsorption characteristics of CO₂ in coal is presented in Fig. 3.

Table 1 Parameters for validation test.

Parameters	Unit	SOB-PL		SIL-PL		BRZ-PL	
		Model A	Model B	Model A	Model B	Model A	Model B
C_{L0}	mol/kg	0.35	0	0.40	0	0.69	0
C_{Lm}	mol/kg	0.87	1.32	0.79	1.19	0.46	1.15
φ	-	35	17.3	39	17.5	77	12
B_L	MPa ⁻¹	3.6	3.6	3.1	3.1	2.95	2.95
m_c	-	10%	10%	6.6%	6.6%	7%	7%

It is shown that the CO₂ adsorption is highest in dry coals, and it reduces significantly in wet coals. For each coal sample, the gas adsorption capacity remains constant after the moisture content exceeds the critical value. A critical moisture content of 10 % for SOB-PL sample, 6.5%

for SIL-PL sample, and 5% for the BRZ-PL sample were estimated from matching experimental data.

It can be seen from Model A that despite the presence of inherent moisture a proportion of the sorption sites can always be occupied by the adsorbed gas molecules. However, Model B presented by Chen et al.²⁸ assumed that the moisture affected gas sorption at all adsorption sites. From Fig.3, it can be seen that both models can predict the overall trends of adsorbed gas concentration as pressure and moisture content increase. But comparing to the results predicted by Chen et al.²⁸, the moisture dependent adsorption model presented in this study shows a better agreement with the experimental results for all coal samples. But the differences between model fitting and laboratory tests are obvious, for example, amount of adsorbed gas at pressure of 0.3 MPa is overestimated. Since, the presence of moisture may affect the heat of adsorption, and pressure constant in conjunction with Langmuir model is associated with heat of adsorption. These deviations from experimental measurements may be attributed to the effects of moisture on the pressure constant B_L .

Fig. 3 Comparison of modeling results with the experimental data of Pajdak⁸ on CO₂ adsorption in coal for different moisture contents (left: Model A and right: Model B).

Both adsorption models, A and B, only consider the moisture-induced variation of volume constant in conjunction with Langmuir model, C_L , and ignore the effects of moisture on pressures constant in conjunction with Langmuir model. Experimental study by Chen et al.²⁰ shows pressures constant is moisture content dependent. Do and Wang⁵³ reported that the rate constant for desorption is related to heat of adsorption and obeys the Arrhenius law. Day et al.¹⁷ and Ozdemir and Schroeder¹¹ showed that the moisture can change the heat of adsorption. Similar to the effects of moisture on volume constant, the following relationship is proposed here to describe the dependence of pressure constant on moisture content:

$$B_L = B_{L0} + B_{Lm} \exp(-\xi m_w) \quad (36)$$

where B_{L0} is the pressure constant that is not affected by moisture, B_{Lm} is the part that can be affected by moisture, and ξ is a weighting coefficient representing the role of moisture in gas desorption.

Combining equation (36) with equation (34) yields a modified Langmuir isotherm (Model C). Although the number of parameters increases for the improved Langmuir isotherm, these parameters can be easily obtained via fitting experimental results. The fitting parameters are listed in Table 2. Considering the dependence of pressure constant in conjunction with Langmuir model on water, the value of C_{L0} increases and that of C_{Lm} drops compared to the values listed in Table 1. The differences between the matched values of coal samples can be attributed to the coal compositions. Fig. 4 shows the comparison using the Model C and it shows an excellent agreement between the experimental measurements and the results predicted by the model. This indicates that the presence of water not only affects the volume constant but also alter the pressure constant. The results demonstrate that the improved model is able to describe gas adsorption behavior in moist coals more accurately.

Table 2 Parameters for validation test using Model C.

Parameters	Unit	SOB-PL	SIL-PL	BRZ-PL
C_{L0}	mol/kg	0.87	0.87	1.0
C_{Lm}	mol/kg	0.45	0.32	0.15
φ	-	38.5	20.4	20.0
B_{L0}	MPa ⁻¹	0.69	0.65	1.17
B_{Lm}	MPa ⁻¹	2.91	2.47	1.77
ξ	-	44	70	114
m_c	-	10%	10%	5%

Fig. 4 Comparison between Model C predicted results with the experimental data of Pajdak⁸ on CO₂ adsorption in coal for different moisture contents.

3.2 Sorption kinetics

In addition to estimating the sorption isotherms, Pajdak⁸ also recorded the CO₂ sorption kinetics of the three coal samples for various moisture content and pressures, e.g., 0.1 MPa, 0.3 MPa, and 0.8 MPa. The experimental results of SOB-PL is used as the benchmark for testing the developed model. A numerical simulation is designed to evaluate the recorded sorption

kinetics of CO₂ in coal.

The samples were crushed and sieved into 0.2–0.25 mm grain size for the tests in Pajdak⁸. For simulation exercises, the coal particles are assumed to be spheres of 0.1125 mm radius, because of symmetry, a 2D circle is used for simulation domain and discretized with triangular mesh. Periodic pressure boundary is assigned on the external surface of the domain for free phase gas: 0.1 MPa for the first 5 hours, 0.3 MPa for the second 5 hours and 0.8 MPa for the last 5 hours. It is assumed that the initial CO₂ concentration in the coal samples is zero. Table 3 lists the material parameters used for this validation test. Some parameters are chosen from published literature. For example, Mastalerz et al.⁵⁶ measured the porosity of coal containing similar vitrinite reflectance to that of the coal from SOB-PL with a value of 0.113. Pore radius, rate constant of desorption and ratio of the rate are obtained by matching the experimental data. The simulation was run for 15 hours. In order to be consistent with the tests, the average adsorption amount of gas over whole domain was used to compare the experimental results, this is achieved via calculating the total adsorbed gas and dividing the total mass at each timestep.

Table 3 Parameters for validating sorption kinetics

Parameters	Value	Unit	Source
Temperature, T	313	K	Pajdak ⁸
Average density of water film, $\bar{\rho}_w$	3.3	g/cm ³	Botan et al. ⁵⁷
Gas molar mass, M	0.044	kg/mol	Given
Molecular diameter of gas, d_m	0.33	nm	Given
Pore radius, r_h	3.0	nm	Fitting
Fractal dimension of the pore surface, d_f	2.0	-	Chen et al. ³⁸
Surface diffusion, D_s^0	1.2e-11	m ² /s	Pajdak ⁸
Ratio of rate constant, w	1.8	-	Fitting
Rate constant of desorption, γ_d	9.5e-3	s ⁻¹	Fitting
Porosity-tortuosity factor, n/τ	4.5e-5	-	Dong et al. ⁵⁸
Porosity, n	0.113	-	Mastalerz et al. ⁵⁶
Coal density, ρ	1410	kg/m ³	Pajdak ⁸

Fig. 5 Comparison between model predicted CO₂ kinetics result with the experimental kinetics results of Pajdak⁸ for the “SOB-PL” coal sample.

Fig. 5 shows the comparison between the experimental data and predicted CO₂ kinetics of the coal sample SOB-PL. It is evident that the model results compare well with the experimental results indicating the capacity of the presented model to describe the sorption and transport processes adequately in moist coal matrices.

4 Model Application

In this section, the presented model is applied to investigate the impacts of moisture on gas transport behaviour in coal matrix. Coal matrix blocks are separated by a natural cleat system (Fig. 6a). When gas is injected into a coal, it firstly flows through the cleat networks and then enters into the matrix, as shown in Fig. 6 (a). In the presented simulations, the matrix blocks are considered to be 1cm by 1cm square domains, and CO₂ is selected as the injected gas. The model domain is discretized with equally sized quadrilateral elements, as shown in Fig. 6 (b).

(b)

Fig. 6 (a) Schematic illustration of CO₂ transport in coal, and (b) discretized model domain and the locations of the observation points.

In order to analyze the effects of gas pressure on the transport behaviour in moist coal matrices, injection gas pressures of 0.5 MPa, 1 MPa and 2MPa are selected as boundary conditions for free gas flow. The fixed gas pressure boundary is converted to the equivalent free gas concentrations using the real gas law and assigned to four external boundaries of domain, as shown in Fig. 6(b). It is assumed that no CO₂ is present initially in the model domain. Two measuring points, p1 (0.2 cm, 0.2 cm) and p2 (0.5 cm, 0.5 cm) are selected to monitor the variations of the gas pressures and adsorbed concentration. Except for pore sizes, parameters used for numerical simulation are chosen from Table 3, which are used for validating adsorption kinetics of CO₂ in Bituminous coals. Experimental observations on pore size distribution revealed that the pore volumes occupied by the pores with size less than 10 nm are significantly more than that by the pores with sizes larger than 10 nm for various rank coals.^{34,59} To consider the permeation of coal matrices, the pore sizes of 0.6 nm, 1 nm, 3 nm and 8 nm are used in these simulations. The corresponding matrix intrinsic permeabilities range from 2.0×10^{-24} to 3.6×10^{-22} m². The dry and moist coal matrices are represented by various moisture contents, e.g., 0.0%, 3.0% and 8.0%.

5. Results and discussions

5.1 Effects of moisture content on gas diffusion in moist coal matrices

The numerical results for gas migration in both dry and moist coals of 3 nm pore sizes and 1 MPa applied boundary pressure are presented here. The results of the other two pore sizes and pressures are similar and hence not repeated. Fig. 7 shows the gas pressure and adsorbed gas distribution within the dry and moist coal matrices after 1 day, 3 days and 5 days simulation period. The temporal evolutions of gas pressure and adsorbed gas concentration at the defined observation points are shown in Fig. 8. Due to gas diffusion from boundaries towards the center of the model domain, both pressure and adsorbed gas in the matrix increases with time. The amount of gas adsorbs in the moist matrix is significantly low. Nonetheless, compared to the transport process in dry coal matrices, the presence of water in coal matrices can speed up the gas flow in coal matrices. These observations agree with the findings of Švábová et al.¹³ and Wang et al.³⁴ After 5 days, gas pressure in the center of the matrix block containing 8.0% moisture content reaches to nearly 0.8 MPa, while it only reaches to 0.4 MPa when the coal matrix is dry. It takes approximately 10 days for gas pressure to reach equilibrium in moist matrices. In contrast, the time for gas pressure to reach equilibrium in dry matrices is around 16 days (Fig. 8a). The maximum adsorbed gas concentration decreases from 1473 mol/m³ to 570 mol/m³ when the coal moisture content increases from 0 to 8.0% (Fig. 8b). This implies that the reduction in sorption capacity with moisture content can lead to more free phase gas in moist coals and formation of larger free gas concentration gradient. This accelerates the free phase gas diffusion into the interior of the coal matrix¹³, although the apparent diffusivity (defined as $\omega_K D_K + \omega_v D_v$) experiences a decrease with an increase in moisture content (Fig. 9). On the other hand, the decrease in adsorption capacity of gases enables the reduction of gas coverage on the pore surface, and the surfaces diffusion decrease is restrained (see Fig. 2). These can explain the why the shorter time is required for reach reach equilibrium in moisturized matrices.

Fig. 7 Gas pressure and adsorbed gas distribution in dry and moist coal matrix after 1, 3, and 5 days.

Fig. 8 Temporal evolutions of (a) gas pressure and (b) adsorbed gas concentration at the observation points p1 and p2.

The results also show that in moist coals gas pressure increases rapidly at the early stages, and in dry coals it rises more gradually with time. This is attributed to larger concentration gradient between the boundary and the interior of the matrix, and due to higher gas diffusivity. With increasing moisture contents (0.0% to 8.0%), apparent diffusivity reduces from $3.56 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ to $2.0 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ initially and from $1.85 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ to $1.25 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ when the equilibrium is reached (Fig. 9). This is because accumulation of water in the matrix pores forms water film and occupies the pore space of coal matrices together with adsorbed gas, leading to a drop of the effective pore size for free phase gas migration.^{30,33} Some studies also reported that the presence of moisture exerted a negative impact on the gas diffusivity^{19,31} or a negative impact at lower moisture content and positive impact at higher moisture content.¹⁴ However, the transport mechanisms for both free phase and adsorbed phase are not considered individually in those works. From Fig. 2, it can be seen that when the the ratio of the rate of blockage to the rate of forward migration in equation (27), w , is less than 1.0, the surface diffusion can drop due to reduction of gas coverage on the pore surface caused by the moisture. Therefore, the changes in gas diffusion behaviour in moist coal matrices may be attributed to moisture effects on both surface diffusion for adsorbed phase and apparent diffusivity for free phase.

For both dry and moist coal matrices, the apparent diffusivity of free gas shows a decreasing trend with increasing time period. Since the pressure inside the coal matrices increases gradually, mean molecular free size is decreased. On the other hand, pore size is reduced by the

coverage of the adsorbed molecule on the pore surface as the pressure rises.³⁸ Compared to the bulk gas diffusivity in dry coals, $1.7 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, the apparent diffusivity is only $0.75 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. It is suggested that the presence of moisture in coal matrices can hinder the decrease in bulk gas diffusivity because of the reduction of gas capacity and pore space occupied by the adsorbed gas.

Fig. 9 Evolution of apparent diffusivity at the p1 and p2 observation points.

5.2 Effects of pressure on the gas diffusion in moist coal matrices

To investigate the effects of pressure on the gas transport process in moist coals, two additional simulations with different pressure boundary conditions are performed. Gas pressures of 0.5 MPa and 2MPa are considered at the boundary of the model domain while the other conditions and parameters remain same as the previous simulations. The evolutions of gas pressure and adsorbed gas concentrations for these boundary conditions are shown in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11, respectively. Obviously, at the lower boundary pressure, the overall gas pressure in the observation points increases gradually, while at the higher boundary pressure, it increases sharply at the early stages. Compared to the required time for pressure reaching equilibrium state at lower gas pressure, the larger boundary gas can shorten the required time slightly. For example, it takes approximately 8 days to reaching the maximum for the 3.0% moisture content when the applied boundary pressure is 2 MPa. Whereas, it takes around 10 days for the boundary pressure of 0.5 MPa. The difference between times required for pressure reaching equilibrium when the matrix contains 8.0% moisture content is not as obvious as that for the lower moisture contents, because increase of moisture content leads to drop of pore size, and further incurring decrease diffusivity of free phase gas, on the other hand, the diffusivity of free gas experiences a more significant decrease with the increase in gas pressure when the pore size is smaller,³⁸ as a result, the required time for reaching gas pressure equilibrium will be

extended slightly.

Fig. 11 shows that for a particular moisture content, at higher gas pressures, more gas is adsorbed. Similar to the pressure evolution, the larger boundary pressures can shorten the time required for adsorbed gas concentration to reach the equilibrium state. Especially when the moisture content is lower. For example, it takes approximately 6 days to reach the maximum adsorbed gas concentration in coal matrix with 3.0% moisture content when the boundary pressure is 2 MPa. But it takes around 10 days for the boundary pressure of 0.5 MPa (Fig. 11a). Interestingly, it can be found that adsorption reaching equilibrium occurs earlier than pressure reaching equilibrium, especially when the moisture content is lower. This suggests the surface diffusion mechanism may play a important role in gas transport in moist coal matrices.

Fig. 10 Evolutions of gas pressure at the observation points for different boundary pressures, and (a) 3.0% moisture content, and (b) 8.0% moisture content.

Fig. 11 Evolutions of adsorbed gas concentrations at the observation points for different boundary pressures and (a) 3.0% moisture content and (b) 8.0% moisture content.

5.3 Effects of pore sizes on the gas diffusion in moist coal matrices

This subsection presents the effects of pore sizes on gas transport processes in a moist coal matrix. Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 show the changes in gas pressure and adsorbed gas concentration

respectively in moist coal matrices with pore sizes of 0.6 nm, 1 nm, 3 nm and 8 nm. It is evident that the gas transport process in coal matrices is significantly affected by the pore sizes. Overall, increase in pore size can shorten the time required for both gas pressure and gas adsorption to reach equilibrium. Fig. 12 (a) shows that it takes approximately 5 days for gas pressures to reach equilibrium in coal matrices with the pore size of 8 nm. However, it takes approximately 20 days in matrices with pore size of 1 nm. When the pore size decreases to 0.6 nm, the gas pressure does not reach to equilibrium even after 20 days. This is because larger pore size can increase the bulk gas diffusivity. The decrease in larger pore size due to presence of moisture film thickness is less than that in smaller pore size. Similar phenomenon has also been observed in the gas adsorption processes.

The effects of moisture on the gas pressure evolution in coal matrices with different pore sizes are different. In 0.6 nm pores, after 5 days, the pressures at the both observation points reach to 0.75 MPa and 0.45 MPa, respectively, when the moisture content is 3.0% (Fig. 12a). Whereas, the gas pressures at the both observation points reach to 0.82 MPa and 0.56 MPa when the moisture content increases to 8.0% (Fig. 12b). In case of 8 nm pores, the pressures at both observation points almost reach equilibrium state simultaneously after 5 days, although the moisture contents remain different. This also implies that the effect of moisture on gas pressure evolution in matrices of smaller pore sizes is more significant. From Fig. 13, it can be seen that the adsorbed gas concentration requires a shorter time to reach equilibrium state than the gas pressure regardless of the pore size. This suggests that the surface diffusion of adsorbed gas may play a dominant role over the free phase diffusion in coal matrices,.

Fig. 12 Evolution of gas pressure at the p1 and p2 observation points of the matrix of different pore sizes with (a) 3.0% moisture content, and (b) 8.0% moisture content.

Fig. 13 Evolution of adsorbed gas concentration at the p1 and p2 observation points of the matrix of different pore sizes with (a) 3.0% moisture content, and (b) 8.0% moisture content.

It is worth mentioning that the pore structure of coals can be altered by the gas adsorption process. Liu et al.⁶⁰ and Hu et al.⁶¹ observed that the specific surface area and volume of coal increased after CO₂ adsorption. Furthermore, pore surface may become smoother and more homogeneous due to gas-coal interaction.⁶² The change in pore surface roughness and coverage will impact the amount of adsorbed gas and surface diffusion, since higher amount of adsorbed gas can reduce the space for free gas migration. Smooth surfaces tend to increase diffusive transport, especially in smaller pores, where the role of Knudsen diffusion becomes important. Smooth surface can lead to reduction of the fractal dimension in equation (8), thereby, increasing Knudsen diffusion.

5.4 Implications for CO₂ sequestration

Coalbeds have been considered as a potential geological formation for CO₂ sequestration. For CO₂ storage process and enhanced coalbed methane recovery, CO₂ injection may lead to a change in water content in coalbeds. Moisture loss can increase the gas adsorption capacity and then increase the total amount of stored gas in coal reservoirs. Different coal ranks have different water-holding capacity and the effects of water on gas adsorption capacity vary across the ranks. Therefore, the moisture dependent adsorption model should be considered when predicting the CO₂ storage capacity and methane content of coal under in-situ conditions.

On the other hand, CO₂ adsorption can stretch pore surface and make coal expand.³ The increase in CO₂ adsorption capacity is able to induce more swelling. It may reduce the cleat apertures as well as the coal permeability, the gas migration in cleat network of coals can be affected. Meanwhile, loss of moisture and coalbed methane displacement by CO₂ can cause shrinkage of coals.¹⁹ Thus, the permeability behaviour of coals containing water is more complex. The

overall swelling/shrinkage of coals due to gas adsorption/desorption and water loss has to be considered for comprehensive understanding of its permeability behaviour. In addition, the findings of this study revealed that the diffusive transfer of gas from cleat network into matrices is not constant in moist coals. Therefore, it is essential to take moisture effects into account when performing reservoir simulations for future predictions.

6 Conclusions

In this work, a real gas transport model is presented to investigate the effects of moisture on transport and adsorption behaviour in moist coals. A moisture-dependent kinetics is presented to study the mass exchange between free gas and adsorbed gas. The validation exercises demonstrated good agreement between the model predicted results and the relevant experimental results collected from literatures. The model is then applied to investigate transport and adsorption behaviour of CO₂ gas in wet coal matrices subjected to different pressure conditions, and pore size distributions. Major findings are summarized as follows:

- (1) The presence of moisture in coal matrices not only significantly reduces the volume constant in conjunction with Langmuir model but also affects the pressure constant. Pressure constant in conjunction with Langmuir model increases with moisture content.
- (2) The apparent diffusivity of bulk gas decreases with moisture content and pressure, but the presence of moisture in coal matrices can hinder the decrease of bulk gas diffusivity.
- (3) Characteristics of pressure and adsorbed gas in wet coal matrices are associated with pressure and pore size. Larger pressure and pore size can shorten the time for reaching equilibrium state. The moisture effect on the time required to reach equilibrium is more significant when pore size is smaller.
- (4) Adsorbed gas concentration reaches to the equilibrium earlier than the gas pressure, and the surface diffusion of adsorbed phase gas may play a dominant role over free phase diffusion in coal matrices.

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NOMENCLATURE

b	= slip coefficient, -
B_L	= reciprocal of pressure constant in conjunction with Langmuir model, 1/Pa
B_{L0}	= part of pressure constant that is not affected by moisture, 1/Pa
B_{Lm}	= part of pressure constant affected by moisture, 1/Pa
C	= concentration of the free gas phase, mol/m ³
C_L	= adsorption capacity of a moist coal, mol/m ³
C_{L0}	= maximum amount of adsorbed gases that is not affected by moisture, mol/m ³
C_{Ld}	= maximum adsorbed phase concentration of dry coals, mol/m ³
C_{Lm}	= maximum amount of adsorbed gases affected by moisture, mol/m ³
C_s	= adsorbed phase concentration, mol/m ³
d_f	= fractal dimension of the pore surface, -
d_m	=molecular diameter, m
D_K	= Knudsen diffusion coefficient, m ² /s
D_s	= surface diffusion coefficient, m ² /s
D_s^0	= surface diffusivity at zero coverage, m ² /s
J_f	= total gas flux in the free phase, mol/m ² /s
J_{fK}	= Knudsen diffusion flux, mol/m ² /s
J_{fv}	= viscous flux, mol/m ² /s
J_s	= surface diffusion flux, mol/m ² /s
K_n	= Knudsen number, -
M	= molar weight, kg/mol
m_c	= critical moisture content of the coal, -
m_w	= moisture content, %
n_e	= effective porosity, -
n	= porosity of coal matrix
R	= universal gas constant, J/mol/K
R_a	=rate of adsorption, mol/m ³ /s
R_d	= rates of desorption, mol/m ³ /s
r_e	= effective radius of a pore, m
r_h	= hydraulic radius of the pore, m
r_w	= equivalent thickness of the water film, m
r_a	= equivalent thickness of the adsorbed gas layer, m
S	= the sink/source representing mass transfer, mol/m ³ /s
S_w	= water saturation, -
T	= absolute temperature, K
u	= gas pressure, Pa
u_L	= pressure constant of Langmuir model, Pa
V_{pv}	= pore volume per unit mass, m ³ /kg
Z	= gas compressibility factor, -
α	= rarefaction coefficient, -
$\bar{\rho}_w$	= average density of water film, kg/m ³
θ	= gas coverage on the wall of matrix pores, -

λ	= mean free path of molecules, m
ω_K	= weighting factor for Knudsen flux, -
ω_v	= weighting factor for viscous flux, -
μ	= gas viscosity, Pa·s
τ	= tortuosity of the medium, -
w	= ratio of the rate of blockage to the rate of forward migration, -
γ_a	=rate constant for adsorption, 1/Pa·1/s
γ_d	=rate constant for desorption, 1/s
φ	= adsorption capacity decay coefficient, -
ξ	= coefficient for effect of moisture on pressure constant of Langmuir model, -

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